

8T – Observables

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Abstract:

By analyzing the setting of the 8T which allowed deriving the primordial, the author builds an analog of the commutation relation and observables of QM using prime pairs. In addition, author expands the idea of matter creation which keeps the manifold stationary and at the same time indicate that Energy is not conserved. That is because matter-anti-matter asymmetry and because matter is a form of energy. However since matter pairs in such way that no curvature exist, the manifold is still stationary given by the anti-commutation relation of fermions.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matrix tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other matrix tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.1). By (1.2A) those manifolds are topologically invariant. Flatness is an immediate result of this framework as given by the illustration below.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2.A)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron by putting it in the fine structure constant formula:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We have described the arbitrary variations of the manifold by the term on the main equation:

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.46)$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term and derived the existence of Fermion. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matric tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

We have presented the spin classification in the 8T thesis, page seventeen, while using the prime critical line:

Spin 0: $2N_0$ variations

Spin $\frac{1}{2}$: $2N_0 + 3$ variations

Spin 1: $2N_0 + 3 + N_V$ variations

Spin N = $2N_0 + 3 + N_{V1} + N_{V2} \dots$ variations

Let us analyze the idea of observables. We know from Quantum mechanics that observables obey a certain operator relations:

$$[\hat{A}, \hat{B}] = \hat{A}\hat{B} - \hat{B}\hat{A} = 0$$

And in cases they do not obey the relation, the result is:

$$\hat{A}\hat{B} - \hat{B}\hat{A} = i\hbar$$

Since we did not use any operators nor we did not use the Planck constants in the theory we need an analog for the idea of observables. To do just than we can replace the bracket used in Quantum mechanics by a prime pair, if those two pairs are vanishing onto zero, i.e. they commute, if they don't, they have a non-vanishing element, isomorphic to a prime or one.

(3,3) (3,5) (3,7) (3,11), (3,13) ...
 (5,3) (5,5) (5,7) (5,11) **(5,13)** ...
 (7,3) (7,5) (7,7) **(7,11)** (7,13) ...
 ...
 (29,19)(29,23), (29,29), **(29,31)**...

All the pairs, which are not marked in yellow, are in commutation relation, i.e. they vanish into zero. As an example:

$$(7,3) - (3,7) = 0$$

The pairs marked in yellow do not commute as they have a non-vanishing element, either prime or one propagating from them. That was the idea which yielded the primorial.

$$(7,11) - (11,7) = +1$$

$$(29,31) - (31,29) = +3$$

...

Those elements propagating from those pairs are violations of stationarity, which are discrete quanta of prime curvature on the matrix tensor. Since those quanta's contain energy, and they obey seemingly no law in which we can predict their propagation, it is than impossible to measure the energy of a system at such scales, or even at all. Not only because of the lack of commutation of those pairs, but also because the manifold arbitrary variations vanish into matter, which has innate energy, given by its mass and mass and energy relation. Therefore, the picture is the following: matter is created by the requirement of a stationary manifold, it does not contradict this condition as it pairs in such way that no curvature is allowed. However, matter is potential curvature, as it is composed by quarks, and for that reason energy can not be conserved. QFT suggested that for each particle of matter created, an anti-particle is also created and so they annihilate each other. That idea implying that there exist equal amounts of matter and anti-matter in the universe, which contradict the experimental data, anti-matter, is much rarer. So that is quite paradoxical, matter creation while the manifold is stationary (due to the anti-commutation relation), and at the same time energy is not conserved, for two reasons: because anti-matter and matter asymmetry and because matter has a potential energy, assuming it has mass.

References

[1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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